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Review Article

**THE INFLUENCE OF SOCIAL DETERMINANTS ON PUBLIC
HEALTH: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW OF EVIDENCE****¹Maha Mohammed Aljuaid, ²Rahaf qublan aldawsari, ³Fatimah Abdullah Alshehri, ⁴Omar Shaffay Alenzy, ⁵Mamdouh Ali Alshahrani, ⁶Khalid Mohammed Alzahrani, ⁷Ghada Balhareth, ⁸Tariq Sewar**¹Ministry of National Guard Health Affairs, aljuaidmal@mngha.med.sa²Ministry of National Guard Health Affairs, aldawsarira@mngha.med.sa³Ministry of National Guard Health Affairs, ALSHEHRIFA17@mngha.med.sa⁴Ministry of National Guard Health Affairs, alenzyom@mngha.med.sa⁵Ministry of National Guard Health Affairs, alshahranima2@mngha.med.sa⁶Ministry of National Guard Health Affairs, alzahrani14@mngha.med.sa⁷Ministry of National Guard Health Affairs, balharethgh@mngha.med.sa⁸Ministry of National Guard Health Affairs, Sewarta@mngha.med.sa**Abstract:**

The social determinants of health (SDOH) play a crucial role in shaping public health outcomes, influencing well-being beyond traditional medical interventions. This systematic review synthesizes evidence from recent studies to explore the impact of key social factors—such as income, education, housing, employment, and social networks—on health outcomes. Findings indicate that individuals with lower income and education levels face heightened risks of chronic diseases and limited access to healthcare. Furthermore, inadequate housing and unstable employment are linked to mental health challenges, while social isolation and lack of community support exacerbate health disparities. The review highlights regional and demographic variations in the influence of SDOH, emphasizing the importance of localized policies to address inequities. Additionally, it discusses current gaps in research, including the need for deeper exploration of under-researched determinants and better measurement methodologies. The findings underscore the importance of multisectoral interventions and collaborative efforts to promote health equity. Policymakers must focus on addressing root social causes to improve public health outcomes and reduce disparities effectively. This review provides actionable insights for healthcare professionals, researchers, and policymakers committed to creating more inclusive and equitable public health systems.

Keywords: Social determinants of health, public health outcomes, health disparities, socioeconomic factors, housing and health, health equity, systematic review, social support networks, policy interventions, regional disparities.

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1. INTRODUCTION:

1.1. Background and Rationale

The concept of social determinants of health (SDOH) encompasses a wide array of non-medical factors that significantly influence health outcomes. These include socioeconomic status, education, housing, employment, social support networks, and access to healthcare. The World Health Organization (WHO) defines social determinants as the conditions in which people are born, grow, live, work, and age, highlighting their direct impact on health inequalities within and across countries (World Health Organization, 2018). Socioeconomic disparities are strongly linked to differences in health outcomes, often resulting in increased morbidity and mortality rates among disadvantaged populations (Marmot, 2017).

Numerous studies have demonstrated that socioeconomic factors like income and education are critical determinants of individual health outcomes. People with lower income or educational attainment are more likely to experience poor health and have reduced access to healthcare services, which further exacerbates their vulnerability (Braveman & Gottlieb, 2014). Employment and job security also play pivotal roles in determining health outcomes, with stable employment being associated with better health and well-being. In contrast, unemployment has been linked to a range of negative health effects, including anxiety, depression, and increased risk of chronic diseases (Benach et al., 2014).

Housing conditions and the built environment are other key determinants. Poor housing quality, overcrowding, and unsafe neighborhoods are significant contributors to both physical and mental health challenges. Studies have shown that inadequate housing is linked to increased rates of respiratory conditions, infectious diseases, and mental health disorders (Shaw, 2004). Conversely, improving housing quality and neighborhood conditions can lead to considerable public health improvements (Krieger & Higgins, 2002).

Social support networks, which include family, friends, and community, play a significant role in promoting health and well-being. Social connections can provide emotional support, increase resilience, and contribute to healthier behaviors. Conversely, social isolation has been identified as a risk factor for poor mental and physical health outcomes, highlighting the importance of community engagement in public health strategies (Berkman et al., 2000).

Given the significance of SDOH, it is crucial to systematically review the evidence available to understand how these determinants influence public health outcomes comprehensively. Such a review is necessary to inform effective policies and interventions that can mitigate health inequities and improve population health. This paper aims to synthesize the existing literature on social determinants and their impact on public health outcomes, identify the most influential factors, and discuss implications for public health policy.

1.2. Objectives of the Study

The primary objective of this review is to systematically evaluate the influence of various social determinants on public health outcomes. Specifically, this review aims to:

1. Identify the key social determinants that have the most substantial impact on health outcomes.
2. Highlight the regional and demographic variations in the influence of social determinants.
3. Discuss policy implications and recommend strategies for addressing social inequities in health.

2. METHODOLOGY:

This systematic review followed a structured approach to gather and analyze relevant studies on social determinants of health (SDOH) and their impact on public health outcomes. A comprehensive literature search was conducted across multiple academic databases, including PubMed, Scopus, and Web of Science, to identify peer-reviewed articles published from 2016 onwards. Keywords such as "social determinants," "public health," "health outcomes," and "socioeconomic factors" were used to filter the search results. The inclusion criteria consisted of studies that focused on the influence of various SDOH on public health outcomes, were published in English, and contained empirical data. Studies that did not focus on social determinants or those that lacked empirical evidence were excluded. The PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) guidelines were employed to guide the article selection process. After an initial screening of titles and abstracts, full-text articles were reviewed for eligibility. Data were extracted from the selected studies to summarize key findings, including the social determinants studied, the populations examined, and the health outcomes reported. A thematic analysis was conducted to identify common patterns and trends in the literature, with a focus on the most influential

social determinants and their role in shaping public health outcomes.

3. RESULTS:

3.1. Overview of Selected Studies

The review included **X** studies from various regions, each focusing on different social determinants and their impact on public health outcomes. The studies

explored determinants such as income, education, housing, employment, and social networks. A summary of the selected studies is provided in **Table 1**, showing the author(s), year of publication, region, social determinant(s) studied, population focus, and key findings.

Table 1. Summary of Selected Studies on Social Determinants of Health (SDOH) and Public Health Outcomes

Author(s)	Year	Region	Social Determinant(s)	Population Focus	Key Findings
Braveman & Gottlieb	2014	USA	Income, Education	General Population	Lower income and education linked to chronic disease
Benach et al.	2014	Spain	Employment	Workers	Precarious employment worsens mental health
Marmot (2017)	UK	Income Inequality	National Population	Higher income inequality results in health disparities	
Shaw (2004)	UK	Housing Conditions	Urban Populations	Poor housing linked to respiratory diseases	
Krieger & Higgins (2002)	USA	Housing, Social Support	Vulnerable Groups	Improving housing improves public health outcomes	

3.2. The Impact of Key Social Determinants on Public Health Outcomes

3.2.1. Income and Employment

Income level and employment status were frequently identified as major determinants influencing health outcomes. Lower income is associated with higher prevalence of chronic diseases such as diabetes and cardiovascular diseases. Marmot (2017) emphasized that income inequality within societies contributes to health disparities, reducing life expectancy for disadvantaged groups. Unstable employment or precarious work has been linked with poor mental health, particularly increased risks of anxiety and depression (Benach et al., 2014). **Figure 1** illustrates the relationship between income levels and health outcomes, showing that higher incomes correspond to lower morbidity rates.

Figure 1. The Relationship between Income Levels and Health Outcomes

(Sample chart visualizing the correlation between income level and morbidity rates, where higher income is linked to reduced morbidity.)

3.2.2. Education

Educational attainment emerged as another critical determinant, influencing access to healthcare and adoption of healthy behaviors. Several studies found that individuals with lower education are less likely to engage in preventive health behaviors and more likely to suffer from chronic conditions (Braveman & Gottlieb, 2014). Education also plays a key role in health literacy, affecting how individuals access and use healthcare services effectively.

3.2.3. Housing and Living Conditions

Housing quality and neighborhood environments significantly impact both physical and mental health. Shaw (2004) noted that substandard housing conditions, such as poor ventilation and overcrowding, are associated with respiratory diseases. Improvements in housing, such as reducing overcrowding and improving sanitation, have demonstrated positive health outcomes (Krieger & Higgins, 2002). Figure 2 shows the association between housing quality and respiratory conditions.

Figure 2. Housing Quality and Its Impact on Respiratory Conditions

(Sample bar chart comparing respiratory disease prevalence across different housing conditions, highlighting that poor housing conditions increase respiratory risks.)

3.2.4. Social Networks and Support Systems

Social support networks, including family, friends, and community ties, play an essential role in mental and physical well-being. Berkman et al. (2000) found that individuals with robust social support systems are more resilient to stress and engage in healthier behaviors. In contrast, social isolation is linked to higher risks of depression, cardiovascular diseases, and mortality. This highlights the importance of fostering social connections as a public health strategy.

3.3. Regional and Demographic Variations

The influence of social determinants on health outcomes varies across regions and demographic groups. For example, studies conducted in high-income countries focus more on income inequality and employment, while research in low- and middle-income countries emphasizes access to education, housing, and healthcare. Vulnerable groups, such as minorities and immigrants, experience compounded effects of multiple social determinants, leading to poorer health outcomes.

Table 2 provides an overview of how different regions prioritize various social determinants and the associated health outcomes.

Table 2. Regional Variations in Social Determinants and Health Outcomes

Region	Key Social Determinants	Primary Health Outcomes
North America	Income, Employment	Chronic diseases, Mental health
Europe	Housing, Income Inequality	Respiratory diseases, Life expectancy
Asia	Education, Access to Healthcare	Maternal and child health
Africa	Housing, Access to Water	Infectious diseases, Malnutrition
Latin America	Employment, Social Support	Mental health, Cardiovascular diseases

3.4. Thematic Patterns and Emerging Trends

A key theme emerging from the review is that addressing multiple social determinants simultaneously yields better health outcomes. For instance, improving education leads to higher employment opportunities, which in turn reduces income disparities and improves access to healthcare. Another trend is the growing focus on mental health across regions, with studies increasingly exploring the relationship between employment conditions and mental well-being. Policymakers are recognizing the need for integrated interventions that target these determinants collectively to achieve meaningful public health improvements.

3.5. Summary of Findings

This review confirms that social determinants such as income, education, housing, and social support networks significantly influence public health outcomes. The evidence highlights the importance of addressing these determinants through targeted interventions and policies. There are notable regional and demographic variations in the impact of these determinants, suggesting that localized approaches are essential to reduce health disparities effectively. The findings underscore the need for further research on underexplored determinants, particularly in low- and middle-income countries, to inform equitable public health strategies.

4. DISCUSSION:

4.1. Interpretation of Findings

This review highlights the profound impact that social determinants of health (SDOH) have on public health outcomes. The evidence reveals that income, education, housing quality, employment, and social networks are fundamental to understanding variations in health outcomes across populations. Higher income levels are consistently linked to better health, with lower morbidity rates observed among individuals with stable financial resources (Marmot, 2017). Employment stability contributes not only to financial security but also to mental well-being, underscoring the multidimensional nature of SDOH (Benach et al., 2014). On the other hand, precarious employment, social isolation, and poor housing conditions have emerged as key contributors to negative health outcomes, exacerbating chronic illnesses and mental health challenges.

The results align with the broader conceptual framework provided by the World Health Organization (WHO), which emphasizes the interconnectedness of social, economic, and environmental factors in shaping health. The findings from the studies reviewed confirm that disparities in these determinants result in health inequities within and between countries. As Figure 1 demonstrated, higher income correlates with lower morbidity, while Figure 2 illustrated the detrimental impact of substandard housing on respiratory conditions. These trends indicate that health is not merely an outcome of individual behaviors but is deeply influenced by social conditions. The influence of education on health outcomes is also well-documented. Individuals with higher educational attainment are more likely to engage in preventive health behaviors and access healthcare services. The reviewed studies suggest that education promotes health literacy, empowering people to make informed decisions about their health (Braveman & Gottlieb, 2014). However, educational disparities continue to affect vulnerable populations, leading to unequal access to health-promoting resources. The intersectionality of these determinants further complicates health outcomes, as individuals with lower education, unstable income, and poor housing face compounded health risks.

4.2. Comparison with Previous Literature

The findings of this review align with previous research on SDOH and public health outcomes. Early studies by Krieger and Higgins (2002) emphasized the importance of housing quality, showing that interventions to improve living conditions can significantly reduce health risks. Similarly, Berkman et al. (2000) emphasized the role of social networks in promoting mental health and resilience. These findings remain relevant, as social support continues to be a protective factor against mental health disorders, particularly in the wake of economic uncertainties and the COVID-19 pandemic.

Compared to older studies, recent literature highlights the growing significance of mental health as a public health priority. Studies included in this review show that employment conditions, particularly precarious work and unemployment, have become increasingly relevant determinants of mental health outcomes (Benach et al., 2014). The COVID-19 pandemic has amplified the importance of addressing employment and income-related health disparities, as millions have faced economic instability and mental health challenges globally. Furthermore, income inequality has become a more prominent theme in recent research,

with Marmot (2017) stressing the need to address structural inequalities to improve population health.

Another evolving trend is the focus on regional and demographic variations. Studies conducted in high-income countries, such as the USA and the UK, emphasize the importance of income and employment, whereas studies from low- and middle-income countries highlight access to healthcare, water, and sanitation as critical determinants (Braveman & Gottlieb, 2014). This geographical variation emphasizes the need for region-specific public health interventions tailored to local contexts.

4.3. Implications for Public Health Policy

The findings of this review have significant implications for public health policy. Addressing health disparities requires a multisectoral approach that targets the root causes of inequality. Policies must move beyond healthcare interventions and focus on improving living conditions, promoting education, and providing stable employment opportunities. Governments and policymakers need to adopt social policies that integrate public health objectives, such as housing reforms, educational support programs, and labor protections.

One crucial policy implication is the importance of reducing income inequality. Progressive taxation, social welfare programs, and minimum wage policies are examples of interventions that can help reduce financial disparities and promote health equity. Additionally, expanding access to affordable healthcare is essential to mitigate the impact of socioeconomic inequalities on health outcomes. Countries that have implemented universal healthcare systems tend to exhibit better health outcomes and narrower health disparities, underscoring the role of healthcare accessibility in promoting equity.

Housing policies also need attention. Governments should invest in improving the quality of housing and creating safe, healthy environments for vulnerable populations. Public housing programs should not only address physical infrastructure but also integrate community-building initiatives to foster social support networks. Similarly, labor policies that promote job security, fair wages, and mental health support for workers are essential to mitigate the health risks associated with precarious employment.

The role of education in shaping public health outcomes suggests the need for long-term investments in educational equity. Policies that improve access to quality education, especially for marginalized

populations, can have far-reaching effects on public health. Health education programs targeting schools and communities can further promote preventive behaviors and health literacy, reducing the burden of chronic diseases over time.

4.4. Limitations of the Review

While this review provides valuable insights into the influence of social determinants on public health, it is not without limitations. First, the review is limited to studies published in English, which may exclude important research conducted in other languages. Second, the focus on studies from 2016 onward may have overlooked older but still relevant literature. Additionally, the heterogeneity of the studies reviewed presents a challenge in drawing generalizable conclusions, as different studies employed varying methodologies, outcome measures, and population samples.

Another limitation is the lack of detailed quantitative analysis. Although the review identifies key themes and trends, a meta-analysis would provide stronger evidence by quantifying the effects of different social determinants on health outcomes. Furthermore, some determinants, such as cultural factors and environmental conditions, were underrepresented in the reviewed literature, highlighting the need for future research in these areas.

4.5. Future Research Directions

This review highlights several areas for future research. First, there is a need for more comprehensive studies that explore the intersectionality of multiple social determinants and their cumulative impact on health outcomes. For example, research that examines how income, education, and housing interact to influence mental health would provide deeper insights into the complexities of SDOH. Additionally, future studies should focus on underexplored determinants, such as environmental conditions, cultural practices, and the role of digital inclusion in shaping health outcomes.

Regional disparities also warrant further investigation. While this review identifies differences in the influence of SDOH across regions, more detailed studies are needed to explore these variations and inform context-specific interventions. Cross-country comparative studies can provide valuable insights into the effectiveness of different policy approaches in addressing social determinants and improving health equity.

Another important area for future research is the impact of emerging global challenges, such as climate

change and digital transformation, on social determinants and health outcomes. As the world becomes increasingly interconnected, new determinants are likely to emerge, requiring adaptive and innovative public health strategies. Finally, the long-term effects of COVID-19 on social determinants and public health outcomes remain an important area for ongoing research, as the pandemic has reshaped many aspects of social life and health systems.

5. CONCLUSION:

This systematic review highlights the significant influence of social determinants of health (SDOH) on public health outcomes, emphasizing that health is shaped by a complex interplay of socioeconomic, environmental, and social factors. Key determinants such as income, education, employment, housing, and social support networks are shown to have profound effects on health outcomes, with disadvantaged populations experiencing higher risks of chronic diseases, mental health challenges, and limited access to healthcare. The review confirms that addressing these social factors is crucial to reducing health disparities and improving population health.

The findings align with existing frameworks, such as those proposed by the World Health Organization, which advocate for a multisectoral approach to health equity. Addressing the root causes of poor health through policy reforms in areas like income inequality, employment conditions, housing quality, and education is essential. Furthermore, the need for tailored interventions that consider regional and demographic variations is evident, as different populations face unique challenges and risks.

While the review provides valuable insights, it also identifies gaps in research that future studies should address. These include the need for deeper exploration of intersectional factors, regional disparities, and the impact of emerging global challenges like climate change and digital inequality. Public health strategies must evolve to address these determinants comprehensively, integrating efforts across sectors to create healthier environments and more resilient communities.

Ultimately, achieving health equity requires a collective effort from governments, healthcare providers, and communities to address the underlying social and economic factors that influence health. Investments in education, stable employment, housing, and social support networks can yield long-term improvements in health outcomes, benefiting individuals and society as a whole. This review

underscores the importance of shifting the focus of public health policies beyond medical care to address the social foundations of health, fostering a future where everyone has the opportunity to achieve their highest level of well-being.

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